

ENERGY EFFICIENT TECHNOLOGIES FOR INDIVIDUAL CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses energy-efficient technologies for individual construction, characteristics of energy-efficient houses, features of passive houses, energy-efficient engineering systems, their advantages, materials used for these systems, and the development of energy-efficient material production in the territory of our country

Introduction. Energy is a beneficial interaction, and its effectiveness increases when considering the sum of actions performed individually by each person. The word "energy," translated from Greek, precisely means "cooperation" or "mutual relation." The reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan and efforts to modernize the economy currently require expanding the introduction of technology and techniques in industrial enterprises, attracting investments, and using them as efficiently as possible. This is because during the transition to a market economy in our country, the emergence of various ownership-based productions and the development of industrial enterprises led to the formation of economic entities such as enterprises, joint-stock companies, branch companies, and limited liability companies. These entities create economic conditions through their investments to integrate their activities into the global community.

Over the past 10-15 years, active discussions, energy-saving programs, theoretical changes, equipment, and experimental models have not significantly impacted the energy density of cities and settlements but have created real conditions for reducing the energy consumption of buildings and facilities. In the 1990s, new housing construction accounted for about 1% annual growth in residential and industrial areas. Therefore, the main potential for energy savings lies in the operational sector through reconstruction and renovation of existing facilities. According to experts' calculations, heat losses in buildings are distributed as follows: up to 40% due to unauthorized use of hot air and unregulated operational regimes; up to 30% due to the low thermal conductivity of enclosed structures; and losses related to

heating systems. Urban planning, architecture, design, construction, engineering, and operation are interconnected and require a systematic approach and economically sound regulation of energy-saving measures. Energy-saving architectural planning solutions relate to planning decisions, especially the ratio of buildings to the total area, the ratio of window glass to exterior walls, the construction of planned buildings, and their relative placement.

The most efficient types of energy-saving exterior walls are multilayer composite structures of walls and cladding using mineral-based materials. The primary reserves of heat saving can be achieved by insulating existing buildings. Heating external walls—being the most expensive and labor-intensive process—can reduce heat loss by approximately 12-15%.

Increasing the efficiency of boiler equipment; eliminating heat losses in district heating networks; modernizing heating and hot water supply systems in buildings; accounting for the housing stock; and regulating energy consumption are essential tasks.

Recommended Measures:

- Use of high-quality boiler equipment that eliminates the need for heat networks when installed on building roofs, including locally produced container-type boiler rooms;
- Transition to automated heat points – besides using jet mixers and pumps, ensuring free and quality regulation of liquid supply. Regulation should consider day and night cycles, winter-autumn-spring periods, weekends, heat demand cycles, etc.
- Transition to automatic control systems, enabling independent switching from centralized heating and dual-tariff electric energy to gas or electric heaters in apartments for hot water supply.
- Installation of heat energy meters measuring up to 25% of the total volume to enable heat energy saving. Consumption for hot water accounts for 8-10%. Measurement and control systems in heating networks help prevent overheating of rooms during temporary temperature increases of outdoor air and indoor conditions, allowing temperature regulation during the heating season (10-12%).

The development of energy-saving buildings traces back to the historical culture of northern peoples, who built homes that retained heat and consumed fewer resources. A classic example of improving energy efficiency in homes is the Russian stove equipped with thick walls for good heat retention and complex flues.

Experiments in modernizing buildings for energy saving date back to 1972 with a building constructed in Manchester, New Hampshire (USA). The building had a cubic shape minimizing the external surface area, with glass areas not exceeding 10%, reducing heat loss through architectural planning solutions. There were no glass claddings on the north side. The flat roof was made in bright colors to reduce heating and, accordingly, reduce ventilation demands in warm seasons. Solar collectors were installed on the roof.

Between 1973 and 1979, the ECONO-HOUSE complex was built in Otaniemi. In addition to complex spatial planning considering location and climate, the building used a special ventilation system that heated air with solar rays collected by specially glazed windows and shutters. Additionally, solar collectors and geothermal devices were integrated into the building's overall heat exchange system. The patches on the roof were designed considering the width of the construction site and the angle of solar radiation at different times of the year.

An interesting scheme for passive house equipment was proposed in May 1988 by Dr. Wolfgang Feist, founder of the Passive House Institute in Darmstadt (Germany), and Professor Bu Adamson from Lund University, Sweden. The concept was developed in many scientific projects funded in Hessen, Germany. The Passive House Institute was established in Darmstadt in 1996.

For construction, environmentally friendly materials are typically chosen, such as traditional aerated concrete, wood, stone, and brick. Recently, passive houses are often built from inorganic waste—recycled concrete, glass, and metal products. Special factories have been built in Germany to convert such waste into construction materials for energy-efficient buildings. Infrared photographs show how effective insulation of a passive house (on the right) is compared to a traditional house.

Experience shows that significant energy savings can be achieved by modernizing most existing buildings under specific conditions and introducing new engineering systems, energy sources, equipment, and energy-saving devices and instruments during operation.

Energy-efficient buildings use complex systems: instead of windows with open panes, hermetically sealed double-glazed soundproof windows are installed, and air and waste ventilation in rooms is centrally managed through heat recovery devices. Additional energy efficiency can be increased if air exits the house and enters through underground air ducts equipped with heat exchangers. The heating device transfers heat from warm air to cold air

References:

1. Berdiyev, O. B., Kurbanov, Z. H., Tilavov, E., Rasulova, N., Boboqulova, S., Jumanov, I., ... & Botirov, B. (2024). The calculation of reinforced concrete conical dome shells considering concrete creep. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 587, p. 03001). EDP Sciences.
2. Hamidduloyevich, K. Z., Ezoza, S., & Jamshid, R. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE MIXTURES USING WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMERS FOR CERAMIC TILES. *Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана*, 2(11), 127-130.
3. Mustafaqulov, J., & Kurbanov, Z. (2024). COMPOSITE GYPSUM MATERIALS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF THERMAL INSULATION PRODUCTS: DEVELOPMENT, PROPERTIES, AND APPLICATIONS. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(10), 124-127.
4. Javohir, M., Zavkiddinjon, K., & Mirzokhid, O. (2024). COMPOSITION AND PHYSICAL AND TECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF CERAMIC CONCRETE WITH INDUSTRIAL WASTE AND CHEMICAL ADDITIVES. *Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation*, 4(1), 38-41.
5. Курбанов, З. Х., Шукруллаева, Д., & Турсунбоева, С. (2024). РАЗРАБОТКА КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ КЛЕЕВЫХ СМЕСЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ВОДОРАСТВОРИМЫХ ПОЛИМЕРОВ ДЛЯ КРЕПЛЕНИЯ МРАМОРНОЙ И ГРАНИТНОЙ ПЛИТКИ. *Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3(12), 158-162.
6. Курбанов, З. Х., Мамадуллаев, Д., & Ибрагимова, К. (2024). РАЗРАБОТКА КЛЕЕВЫХ СМЕСЕЙ ДЛЯ УКЛАДКИ КЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ ПЛИТ НА ОСНОВЕ ЦЕМЕНТА С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ВОДОРАСТВОРИМЫХ ПОЛИМЕРОВ. *Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана*, 2(11), 80-83.
7. Hamidduloyevich, K. Z., Vohid, X., & Gulchehra, R. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE MIXTURES USING WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMERS BASED ON CEMENT. *Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3(12), 97-100.

8. Kurbanov, Z., & Noryigitov, N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE MIXTURES FOR CERAMIC TILE INSTALLATION USING WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMERS BASED ON CEMENT. Central Asian Journal of Academic Research, 2(12), 79-82.
9. Hamidduloyevich, K. Z., & Laziz, S. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE ADHESIVE MIXTURES FOR CERAMIC TILE INSTALLATION USING WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMERS. Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана, 2(12), 22-25.
10. Hamidduloyevich, K. Z., & Sitora, Y. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITION AND TECHNOLOGY FOR PRODUCING COMPOSITE WATER-RESISTANT FOAM GYPSUM MATERIALS BASED ON SULFATE-CONTAINING MINERAL BINDERS. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана, 2(11), 76-79.
11. Hamidduloyevich, K. Z., & Bekzod, Q. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE ADHESIVE MIXTURES FOR LAYING CERAMIC TILES USING WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMER. Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation, 3(12), 92-96.
12. Абдусаматов, К. Б., Турсунов, Б. А., Курбонов, З. Х., Расулова, Н. Б., Убайдуллаев, Ж. А., Бахронов, Ж. Т., ... & Каримов, Л. Ш. (2021). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОТХОДОВ АСБЕСТОЦЕМЕНТОВ ПРИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ ГАЗОБЕТОННЫХ БЛОКОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.
13. Khamidulloevich, K. Z., Botirkulovna, R. N., Narzullayeva, K., & Davron, O. (2023). Study of the Mechanical Properties of High Strength Concrete Obtained With the Help of Chemical Additives. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(2), 64-68.
14. Талипов, Н., Курбанов, З., & Артыккулов, Д. (2023). ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СУХИЕ СМЕСИ С ПОЛИМЕРНЫМИ ДОБАВКАМИ. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(5), 43-48.
15. Kurbanov, Z., & Artiqulov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF DRY CONSTRUCTION MIXED ON THE BASIS OF LOCAL MARBLE WASTE POWDER. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(9), 104-106